

PROBLEMS AND STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE LISTENING COMPETENCE FOR LAW STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of listening skills and some problems related to understanding legal concept for the students of law. Moreover, researches and strategies by foreign scientist and professionals on improving listening and understanding legal terminology also using them in real situations are explored in the article.*

Key words. *Listening competence, non-English speaking environment, international labor market, legal professions, modelling, listening techniques, organizing interviews, audiobooks, legal concepts, legalese, courtroom language, interact with clients, communication strategies, legal podcasts.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ И СТРАТЕГИИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ АУДИРОВАНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ ЮРИДА

Аннотация. *В данной статье обсуждается важность навыков слушания и некоторые проблемы, связанные с пониманием правовой концепции для студентов-юристов. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются исследования и стратегии зарубежных ученых и специалистов по улучшению слушания и понимания юридической терминологии, а также ее использования в реальных ситуациях.*

Ключевые слова: *Аудирование, неанглоязычная среда, международный рынок труда, юридические профессии, моделирование, методы слушания, организация интервью, аудиокниги, юридические концепции, юридический язык, язык в зале суда, взаимодействие с клиентами, стратегии общения, юридические подкасты.*

One of the most significant abilities for communicating in everyday life is skills of listening. Being able to follow a speaker in a foreign language and responding in an appropriate way should be taught like all other language skills. However, teaching listening skills is possibly the most difficult part of EFL teachers' work. Especially it is much harder when you teach listening skills for specific purposes in a non-English speaking environment.

One of the spheres where listening skills are considered to be highly important is Law.

Knowing a foreign language and mastering different competences, especially, listening skills plays a crucial role in preparing of competitive and well-educated specialists who can be successfully accepted professionals in the international labor market. English is widely used in the area of law and legal profession. The people who work in legal professions use English for different purposes such as education, for their work (especially in today's era of globalization), for

getting promotion and for recreation. They have to master speaking, listening comprehensions also writing and translating activities in English language in different formal and informal situations.

Therefore, educator's attention should be drawn to enhance students' listening skills and integrating it with classroom environment. There are some methods to help teachers and students to improve their listening comprehension.

First, the most effective method which can help teachers to show their students how to do something in a right way is definitely modelling. It also means showing how to do something in a successful and less successful ways, have discussions with students about the processes and challenges they faced during the activity. In this way students will be given a chance to begin learning by seeing and hearing in real situations. "Modelling of listening techniques makes effective practices visible to students," writes Professor Neil Hamilton in his law review article "Effectiveness Requires Listening: How to Assess and Improve Listening Skills". Organizing interviews with clients who needs legal advice or consulting during class time would be a good example for students which assists them to improve both their professional and communicative knowledge and this method can be a good investment that can show amazing results immediately. If students will be given an opportunity to see and discuss effective listening during these modelled interviews they are far more likely to act in the same way in their own work with their real clients.

Another useful way which helps law students to improve their listening is using audiobooks that include legal topics or are written in legal contexts. When students listen to these materials it will help them to become more attentive to the pronunciation, intonation and vocabulary of legal language. As legal English is a lot more difficult than general English, it is also necessary for lawyers to know meanings of various legal term and analyze them simultaneously while listening.

Audiobooks expose listeners to native speakers or professional narrators who pronounce legal texts and terms in a clear way and they also improve students understanding of spoken legalese, making it easier to follow discussions in the courtroom during trials and be open to interact with clients.

Listening to audiobooks and imitating to legal patterns students can refine their own pronunciation and as well as speaking skills which is especially important for lawyers when they appear in the courtroom or while giving consultations to clients. Another useful aspect of audiobooks is that they give you an opportunity to use your time more effectively. You can commute to work or your study, do workouts or other activities while listening to legal materials, utilizing that moments to improve your language competences. For law students who want to improve their legal English through listening, following audiobooks are recommended.

1. "The Law of Law School". As the name suggests this is one of the most exclusive books which is aimed specially for students who are studying law. It is also essential guidebook for the first year of law school and therefore it can be added to the category of best audiobooks for law students.

2. "Legal English for Lawyers-listening and speaking". It is an audiobook which can be considered as a source that covers in-depth different kinds of legal terminology, language used in the courtroom and the most effective communication strategies for lawyers. Listening to this

audiobook enables students to enhance their knowledge on legal English skills and assist them to be more confident and competitive in their legal career.

In conclusion, according to the information given above we can see that there are several methods which help both EFL teachers and their law students with improving their listening skills and be more independent while working in the sphere of law. Modelling and imitating to lawyer-client interviews or courtroom procedures enable students to listen to the legal English and immerse in this kind of atmosphere without struggling listening legal terminology and using them in the real life. Moreover, listening to Legal audiobooks or legal podcasts can be a valuable addition to students' language improvement strategies. Listening to these kind of legal materials help students to be familiar with spoken legalese, including pronunciation, intonation. Teachers should pay more attention to introduce these kind of advantageous strategies in their lessons to make sure that their students can deal with problems related to listening and understanding legal concepts.

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